

Synthesis, characterization and equilibrium studies of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of tetraaza macrocycles derived from dichloromethane

Ankur Rastogi, Anurag and Ram Nayan*

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : ramnayan_2003@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 22 September 2008, revised 2 April 2009, accepted 27 April 2009

Abstract : The template condensation between dichloromethane and diamines (1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane) in presence of nickel(II) and copper(II) ions are described. Formation of the new complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{TACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{TACD})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of the macrocycles 1,3,6,8-tetraazacyclodecane (TACD) and 1,3,7,9-tetraazacyclododecane (TADD) and the ligand hydrochlorides TACD.4HCl and TADD.4HCl has been supported by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements and spectral studies. Potentiometric equilibrium studies on the TACD and TADD hydrochlorides and their metal complexes with nickel(II) and copper(II) also support the structures. The high values of stability constants obtained are also in favour of cyclic structures of the molecules.

Keywords : Dichloromethane, copper(II), nickel(II), macrocycles, complex.

Introduction

The reaction of equimolar amounts of the tetrachloromethane, diamines (1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane) and nickel hydroxide in *n*-butanol studied earlier led to the formation of mononuclear nickel(II) complexes of 1,5,6,8-tetraaza-2,2,7,7-tetrachlorocyclodecane (TTCE) and 1,3,7,9-tetraaza-2,2,8,8-tetrachlorocyclododecane (TTDE)¹. About 50% nickel hydroxide remains unreacted in each system. But, under the similar experimental condition a 25-membered new cyclic ring 1,3,6,8,11,13,16,18,21,23-decaaza-2,2,7,7,12,12,17,17,22,22-decachlorocyclopentacosane (DDCP) is generated in the condensation reaction between 1,2-diaminoethane and tetrachloromethane in presence of copper(II) ion. Five copper(II) ions each coordinated to two aza donors are accommodated in the ring cavity². Also, a dinuclear new product of TTDE³ $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TTDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is obtained from equimolar reaction mixture of copper hydroxide, 1,3-diaminopropane and tetrachloromethane. The present work is the extension of the diamine condensation reaction to dichloromethane (Fig. 1).

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals obtained as reagent grade were used without further purification.

Chemical and physical measurements :

Microanalyses of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The metal content of the macrocyclic complexes were determined by EDTA titrations⁴ as described earlier². The amount of ionizable chloride ion was determined by conductometric titrations³ with the help of a DDR conductivity meter (type 304). The infrared spectra in the range 4000–250 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. A Jeol D-300 (EI/CI) mass spectrometer was employed for obtaining mass spectra of the ligand hydrochlorides.

General synthetic procedure :

Template condensation of 1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane with dichloromethane were carried out in the presence of nickel or copper hydroxide. The reaction mixture was refluxed in a round bottomed flask using *n*-butanol as solvent. The colour change proved to be indicative of complex formation. Products were extracted in water, concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution yielded the product. The crystals were then washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60 °C) and dried under reduced pressure. The metal free macrocycle hydrochlorides were obtained by removing copper(II) ions from the acidified copper(II) complexes.

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complex of 1,3,6,8-tetraazacyclodecane (TACD) :

A mixture of nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.91 mmol), 1,2-diaminoethane (6.48 g, 107.82 mmol) and dichloromethane (9.16 g, 107.85 mmol) in 200 mL butanol was refluxed for 4 h. The mixture initially contain-

ing light green precipitate changed to yellowish-green turbid solution after 15 min. The mixture then gradually changed to a mixture of violetish-red and light green precipitates. The resulting content was treated with 150 mL of water and filtered. The light green residue on filter paper was rejected. The filtrate contained colourless non-aqueous layer and reddish-pink aqueous layer containing the macrocyclic product. Concentration and refrigeration of aqueous layer yielded violet crystals. The crystals are moderately soluble in water, but their solubility is poor in methanol or acetone. Washing of the crystals with methanol followed by acetone gave analytically pure crystals, yield 1.8 g.

Synthesis of copper(II) complex of 1,3,6,8-tetraazacyclodecane (TACD) :

A mixture of copper hydroxide (6.00 g, 61.50 mmol), 1,2-diaminoethane (7.39 g, 122.96 mmol) and dichloromethane (10.45 g, 123.04 mmol) in 200 mL *n*-butanol was warmed and stirred for 15 min after which a bluish-violet solution was obtained. The resulting solution was refluxed for 6 h during which time its colour changed from bluish-violet to violet. The colour change indicated condensation of coordinated amines with CH_2Cl_2 yielding the cyclic product. The violet solution was treated with 150 mL water and filtered. Small amount of a brownish-black precipitate on filter paper was rejected. Violet aqueous layer of the filtrate was separated from the very light yellowish-violet non-aqueous layer. Concentration and refrigeration of the violet aqueous solution yielded the crude crystals of the product associated with some sticky material. The sticky material was insoluble in either benzene or butanol. But, the impurity was removed by treating the crude product with a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (1 : 1). This solvent mixture was added to the crude product placed on filter paper. Violet spots appeared on the filter paper due to absorption of the impurity. Taking fresh paper and the same solvent, the process was repeated till the filter paper was found spot free. Thus, pure violet crystals of the macrocyclic ligand complex were obtained, yield 4.8 g.

Synthesis of copper(II) complexes of 1,3,7,9-tetraazacyclododecane (TADD) :

Condensation of 1,3-diaminopropane and dichloromethane in presence of copper hydroxide were carried out taking different ratios of the reagents in order to obtain mononuclear and dinuclear complex molecule. In the first experiment the reaction mixture containing 8.00 g (82.00 mmol) copper hydroxide, 6.08 g (82.02 mmol) 1,3-diaminopropane and 6.96 g (81.95 mmol) dichloro-

methane in 200 mL *n*-butanol was refluxed for ~6 h. The initial mixture consisting deep blue copper(II)-1,3-diaminopropane complex solution and copper hydroxide precipitate changed to violet turbid mixture just after 5 min of heating. The mixture is then changed to a bluish-violet mixture after 6 h of heating. Further, the mixture was cooled, treated with 150 mL of water. The bluish violet aqueous layer containing macrocyclic compound was separated from blackish-green residue and very light non-aqueous layer as described in other systems. The aqueous solution gave greenish-violet sticky crystals after concentration and refrigeration. The sticky material was almost removed by treating the impure crystals with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) mixture on filter paper. Finally, analytically pure deep bluish-violet crystals were obtained by washing with methanol (yield 2.9 g).

In the second experiment, a new reaction mixture containing 6.00 g (61.50 mmol) copper hydroxide, 9.12 g (123.03 mmol) 1,3-diaminopropane and 10.45 g (123.04 mmol) dichloromethane in 200 mL butanol was refluxed for 5 h and 30 min. The reaction mixture similar to that in first experiment gradually changed to a bluish-violet turbid mixture at the end of heating. On treatment with 150 mL of water and separation of solid residue, non-aqueous and aqueous layers, it was observed that the residue is brown and is in small quantity. The non-aqueous layer was very light reddish-violet, while aqueous solution was bluish-violet. Finally, bluish-violet crystals, yield 1.5 g, were obtained from the aqueous solution by the procedure described in the first experiment.

An unsuccessful attempt was made to prepare nickel(II) complex of TADD from a mixture of 5.00 g (53.92 mmol) nickel hydroxide, 7.99 g (107.78 mmol) 1,3-diaminopropane and 9.16 g (107.85 mmol) dichloromethane in 200 mL butanol refluxed for 2 h. After 20 min of heating, the colour of the mixture changed from light green to light blue and finally, at the end of the condensation to bluish violet. The expected product, bluish-violet, was extracted in water as copper(II) system. However, the product could not be isolated from the aqueous solution.

Preparation of metal free macrocycles :

The copper(II) complexes of 1,3,6,8-tetraazacyclodecane $[\text{Cu}(\text{TACD})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.50 g, 4.28 mmol) and 1,3,7,9-tetraazacyclododecane $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.50 g, 2.73 mmol) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2$ (1.00 g, 3.26 mmol) were separately dissolved each in 50 mL of water. These solutions were acidified with conc. HCl (5 mL, 12 N) and H_2S gas was passed into these solutions for about 15 min. The black CuS was separated by filtra-

tion, and the presence of the Cu^{2+} ion in the filtrate was checked by again passing H_2S gas into it. The filtrate was further boiled for 2–3 min in order to remove the dissolved H_2S gas. The filtrates containing hydrochlorides of the macrocycles were concentrated and kept at room temperature (25 °C, for 15 days) for crystallization. The crystallized products $\text{TACD} \cdot 4\text{HCl}$ (NaCl like crystals, white) and $\text{TADD} \cdot 4\text{HCl}$ (flat, but needle shaped transparent crystals; same product from both complexes) were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 1.20 and 0.82 g (from the dinuclear complex), respectively.

Potentiometric titrations :

The following mixtures : (i) 0.002159 N HNO_3 ; (ii) 0.0005 M $\text{TACD} \cdot 4\text{HCl}$ or $\text{TADD} \cdot 4\text{HCl}$ + (i); (iii) 0.0005 M nickel/copper nitrate + (ii); and (iv) 0.0005 M $[\text{Ni}(\text{TACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}/[\text{Cu}(\text{TACD})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}/[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2 + 0.002$ M HCl + (i) were titrated pH-metrically at 25 °C and at ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO_3) using CO_2 -free 0.1770 N NaOH solution. A pH-meter (EC 5656) with combined electrode system was employed for titration. The initial volume of each mixture was kept 50 mL. From experimental data, titration curves (pH vs moles of alkali used per mole of ligand, *a*) were plotted and analysed^{5,6}. The titration curve of mixture (iv) coincides with that of mixture (iii) in each metal-ligand system.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The template reaction involving metal hydroxide, dichloromethane and diamine (1,2-diaminoethane or 1,3-diaminopropane) in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio yields mononuclear complexes. The 1 : 2, metal-ammine complex, probably present in large excess as compared to 1 : 1, metal-ammine complex, condenses with dichloromethane. The generated 1,3,6,8-tetraazacyclodecane (TACD) or 1,3,7,9-tetraazacyclododecane (TADD) macrocycles are coordinated to copper(II) or nickel(II) ion through their four aza donors (Fig. 1).

The reaction of equimolar amounts of 1,3-diaminopropane, dichloromethane and copper hydroxide initially leads to the formation of blue 1 : 1, metal-ammine complex. On refluxing the reaction mixture condensation of the coordinated amine and dichloromethane proceeds, followed by a colour change, yielding dinuclear complex of the 12-membered tetraazamacrocyclic TADD. Cyclization, through template condensation, yielding a product with one molecule of each reactant 1,3-

diaminopropane and dichloromethane is unlikely to occur as the resulting smallest cavity of the product cannot accommodate the copper(II) ion. $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is formed by involvement of two molecules of each 1,3-diamino-propane and dichloromethane. The complex is structurally similar to earlier reported dinuclear complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TTDE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ derived from condensation of equimolar amounts of copper hydroxide, 1,3-diamino-propane and carbon tetrachloride³.

The compounds were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, and infrared, nuclear magnetic resonance and mass spectral studies. The results of elemental analyses reported in Table 1 indicate the stoichiometry which is in agreement with the formulation given. The IR results are strongly suggestive of the cyclic nature of the macromolecules due to the absence of bands due to coordinated or free $-\text{NH}_2$ groups⁷⁻⁹.

The presence of coordinated water is indicated by the appearance of a very strong and broad band at 3250 cm^{-1} . Bands at 1640 , 630 and 520 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\delta(\text{O}-\text{H})$, $\text{O}-\text{H}$ wagging and $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{O})$, respectively. Many other strong/medium/weak bands at 1600 , 1360 , 1320 , 1260 , 1140 , 1070 , 1010 , 965 , 862 , 810 , 630 , 465 and 392 cm^{-1} are associated with the skeletal vibrations of the whole complex molecule.

In the infrared spectrum of copper-TACD complex bands attributed to C-H groups are observed at 2955 , 2887 and 1386 cm^{-1} (asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring, respectively). The $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ mode of the secondary amine is seen at 3134 cm^{-1} . Another band appears at 1585 cm^{-1} due to bending mode of NH group. Presence of water molecule in the complex is indicated by the appearance of a very strong band at 3250 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$ bands are seen at 1043 and 468 cm^{-1} respectively.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for TACD and TADD systems

Compd.	Yield (%) (Colour)	D.p./M.p.* (Colour at D.p)	Δ_M (Ω^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1})	Analysis (%) :					Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				Found (Calcd.)					
				C	H	N	Ni/Cu	Cl ^b	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{TACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	8.7	250	265	18.92 (18.86)	7.42 (7.40)	14.72 (14.67)	15.32 (15.37)	18.50 (18.56)	- (382.0)
$\text{NiC}_6\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2$	(Violet)	(Black)							
$[\text{Cu}(\text{TACD})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	22.3	180	259	20.46 (20.54)	6.90 (6.91)	16.04 (15.98)	18.18 (18.11)	20.28 (20.21)	- (350.8)
$\text{Cu}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	(Violet)	(Dark violet) ^a							
TACD.4HCl	96.8	280	-	24.76 (24.85)	6.98 (6.97)	19.30 (19.32)	-	48.72 (48.89)	145 (290.0)
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4 \cdot 4\text{HCl}$	(White)	(Light brown)							
$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	12.9	220	416	17.45 (17.49)	5.86 (5.88)	10.16 (10.20)	23.06 (23.13)	25.75 (25.81)	- (549.3)
$\text{Cu}_2\text{C}_8\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_4$	(Deep bluish-violet)	(Black)							
$[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2$	8.0	170	218	31.39 (31.32)	6.56 (6.58)	18.34 (18.27)	20.78 (20.71)	23.06 (23.11)	- (306.8)
$\text{CuC}_8\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$	(Bluish-violet)	(Black)							
TADD.4HCl	94.3	203*	-	30.16 (30.20)	7.64 (7.62)	17.55 (17.61)	-	44.50 (44.57)	318 (318.2)
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4 \cdot 4\text{HCl}$	(Colourless)	(-)							

^aBrown at $230\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and dark brown at $322\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, ^bionizable chloride ion.

Infrared spectra :

TACD systems :

In the infrared spectrum of the nickel(II)-TACD complex, a shoulder of N-H stretching mode of only secondary amine groups appears at 3140 cm^{-1} . The compound exhibits $\delta(\text{N}-\text{H})$ vibration at 1580 cm^{-1} . Weak bands at 1080 and 465 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N})$, respectively. Strong but very sharp bands for C-H symmetric, asymmetric stretching and scissoring vibrations are seen at 2852 , 2920 and 1450 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The metal free TACD hydrochloride exhibits very strong but broad C-H asymmetric and symmetric stretching and a very weak but sharp scissoring bands at 3000 , 2889 and 1388 cm^{-1} , respectively. The presence of bands attributed to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\delta(\text{N}-\text{H})$ modes of secondary amines are seen at 3192 and 1597 cm^{-1} , respectively. A medium but very sharp band at 1082 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$. Like most amino acids and their hydrochlorides, the ligand hydrochloride exhibits a complex series of weak or very weak but generally sharp bands at 2797 , 2673 ,

2580, 2511, 2418 and 2285 cm^{-1} and a prominent band at 2052 cm^{-1} (medium but very sharp).

TADD systems :

The infrared spectrum of the dimeric complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is strongly suggestive of the cyclic nature of the complex, due to the absence of a band attributed to a primary amino group. The N-H stretching mode of the secondary amino group is seen as a weak shoulder at 3150 cm^{-1} . Another band appearing at 1585 cm^{-1} is due to bending mode of secondary amine group. The complex exhibits a weak but very sharp band at 2875 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 2930 cm^{-1} . These bands are assigned to symmetric and asymmetric C-H stretching vibrations, respectively. A strong C-H scissoring peak appears at 1380 cm^{-1} . The presence of coordinated water molecule in the complex is indicated by the appearance of a strong band at 3250 cm^{-1} followed by other peaks at 818 (weak but very sharp), 660 (medium but sharp) and 588 cm^{-1} (weak but sharp) assigned to O-H stretching, rocking, wagging and Cu-O(H_2O) stretching, respectively. A very weak shoulder at 442 cm^{-1} and a weak but very sharp band at 1090 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$, respectively.

In the infrared spectrum of the mononuclear $[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2$ complex bands attributed to functional groups are observed at the following frequencies (cm^{-1}) : 2920, 2870 and 1375 (C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching) and 1580 cm^{-1} (N-H bending). Bonding of copper to ligand through nitrogen is indicated by a medium but very sharp peak at 488 cm^{-1} .

The metal-free macrocyclic molecule, TADD.4HCl, exhibits a very strong band at 3014 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 2893 cm^{-1} which are assigned to asymmetric and symmetric C-H stretching vibrations, respectively. A C-H scissoring peak appears at 1466 cm^{-1} . A $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration for secondary amine is seen at 3220 cm^{-1} (very weak shoulder). A weak but sharp peak at 1599 cm^{-1} may be attributed to N-H bending vibration. A series of weak or very weak bands at 2775, 2692, 2652, 2557, 2494, 2407, 2301 and 2251 cm^{-1} and prominent medium but very sharp band at 2017 cm^{-1} are associated with the $>\text{NH}_2^+\text{Cl}^-$ group. Other important bands at 1402, 1188, 1103, 1032, 943, 833, 777, 446, 418 and 407 cm^{-1} may be attributed to ligand skeletal vibrations.

Comparison of the TACD and TADD complexes with other systems :

The complexes of the chloro derivatives of TACD,

and TADD, 1,3,6,8-tetraaza-2,2,7,7-tetrachlorocyclodecane (TTCE)¹ and 1,3,7,9-tetraaza-2,2,8,8-tetrachlorocyclododecane (TTDE)³, respectively have been reported in earlier publications. In the nickel complexes of TTCE, TTDE and TACD the N-H or N-C stretching frequency order follows : TTDE < TACD < TTCE. But, the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration order is reversed, TTDE > TACD > TTCE. A comparison of the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ of TTDE and TTCE complexes indicates that the complexes with alternate four- and six-membered fused rings are most stable than four- and five-membered ring systems. The strong inductive effect of the two Cl atoms bound to the same C atom in the TTCE complex appears to be responsible for the reduction of the Ni-N bond order ($\nu(\text{Ni-N}) = 442 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as compared to that in nickel-TACD system reported above.

The ring size of the macrocycles TADD and TTDE is identical. But, a comparison of the $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ in the dimeric copper complexes with TADD and TTDE follows the bond order : TADD > TTDE. The lower Cu-N bond order in TTDE system ($\nu(\text{Cu-N}) = 380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)³ is due to electron withdrawing effect of the four Cl atoms. In view of greater stability of the four- and six-membered fused ring than four- and five-membered fused ring systems, the $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ frequency in monomeric copper complexes of TADD and TACD appear at 488 and 468 cm^{-1} , respectively. The higher frequency in TADD system is due to the presence of additional electron donating methylene groups. Also, as expected the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration frequency follows the order : TADD > TACD. The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ in the infrared spectrum of the monomeric metal complex of TACD is observed at 465 cm^{-1} . Comparatively high frequency in copper system is due to stronger electron accepting property of copper than nickel. In the dinuclear copper complex with TADD, the two copper ions (each bonded to only two nitrogen atoms) are not well fitted in the ring cavity and therefore, the bond order (shown by $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ vibrations at lower frequency, 442 cm^{-1}) as compared to that in the mononuclear copper complexes with TADD or TACD is low.

¹H NMR spectra :

Additional structural evidence for the ligands has been obtained from the ¹H NMR spectra of their hydrochlorides. The spectrum of TADD.4HCl can be resolved into three distinct regions corresponding to the resonances resulting from NH_2^+ and CH_2 protons. The spectrum shows broad triplet centered at 3.15 ppm and a second broad multiplet centered at 2.11 ppm (*J* 7.8 Hz). The triplet

resonance is ascribed to the α protons whereas the broad upfield multiplet is assigned to the β protons. The NH_2^+ proton resonances appear as a broad singlet centered at 4.90 ppm. The position of NH_2^+ proton resonance is in close agreement with those reported for NH proton resonances in structurally similar aza complexes⁸. The integrations of signals yield proton ratios 1 : 2 : 3 for (β CH_2) : (α CH_2) : ($\text{NH}_2^+ + \text{CH}_2$, between two NH_2^+ groups). In the spectrum of nickel-TACD complex, a broad signal in the region 4.70–4.65 ppm is observed for NH and H_2O protons. On the basis of relative areas, the two upfield signals (doublets) in the region 4.14–4.04 and 3.73–3.30 ppm are expected for resonances resulting from CH_2 and $\text{CH}_2.\text{CH}_2$ protons, respectively.

Mass spectra :

Determination of the molecular weight by mass spectra of the ligand hydrochlorides TACD.4HCl and TADD.4HCl (EIMS) has been very useful in completing their characterization. The highest mass peak found in the spectrum of TADD.4HCl occurs at m/z value equal to its molecular ion (Table 1). But, the corresponding peak in TACD.4HCl deviates from their calculated molecular weight. The mass loss corresponds to four molecules of

HCl attached with the macrocycle through weak coordinate bonds^{3,10}. A representation of mass spectrum of TACD.4HCl and the fragmentation pattern observed therein is shown in Fig. 2. Different fragments and their masses and percentage abundances observed in the mass spectra of ligand hydrochlorides are given below :

TADD.4HCl ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4.4\text{HCl}$) : 44 ($[\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N} + \text{H}]^+$, 37.3%); 57 ($[\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{N}]^+$, 100%); 127 ($[\text{C}_7\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{-H}]^+$, 2.23%); 160 ($[\text{C}_8\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3 + 3\text{H}]^+$, 0.2%); 176 ($[\text{M-4HCl} + 4\text{H}]^+$, 0.1%); 210 ($[\text{M-3HCl} + \text{H}]^+$, 0.5%); 283 ($[\text{M-HCl} + \text{H}]^+$, 0.1%); 318 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 0.3%).

TACD.4HCl ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4.4\text{HCl}$) : 43 ($[\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}]^+$, 100%); 58 ($[\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_2]^+$, 32.8%); 90 ($[\text{C}_3\text{H}_9\text{N}_3 + 4\text{H}]^+$, 2%); 118 ($[\text{C}_5\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3 + 3\text{H}]^+$, 3.2%); 145 ($[\text{M-4HCl} + \text{H}]^+$, 31.34%).

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

The ligand hydrochloride TADD.4HCl melts at 203 °C but other compounds decompose in the 170–250 °C range. The complexes of the TACD and TADD are violet and bluish-violet, respectively. All the compounds are highly soluble in water due to their ionic nature. Most of them are also soluble in other polar solvents, like methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. $[\text{Ni}(\text{TACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$

Fig. 2. Fragmentation pattern observed in the mass spectrum of TACD.4HCl.

Fig. 3. pH vs a curves (1) TADD 4HCl, (2) TACD 4HCl, (3) Ni^{2+} -TADD 4HCl, (4) Ni^{2+} -TACD 4HCl, (5) Cu^{2+} -TADD 4HCl and (6) Cu^{2+} -TACD 4HCl

$\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{TADD})]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{TACD})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibit molar conductance values in the $218\text{--}265 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ range, and are 2 : 1 electrolytes. Similarly, the molar conductance ($416 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) obtained for $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TADD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is consistent with its formulation.

Solution stability :

The pH vs a curve of TACD.4HCl (Fig. 3) shows a weak inflection at $a = 2.0$ and the highest a value obtained under the experimental pH condition 3.63. But, there is no inflection in the corresponding curve of TADD.4HCl due to coexistence of the protonated species H_4A^{4+} , H_3A^{3+} , H_2A^{2+} and HA^+ . The evaluated proton-ligand hydrochloride dissociation constants for both ligand systems are given in Table 2. In absence of pH vs a curve beyond $a = 2.60$ (pH ~ 11.0 , highest experimental pH) in TADD system, the fourth proton-ligand hydrochloride dissociation constant value could not be obtained.

Formation of non-protonated tetraaza-macrocyclic complex MA^{2+} of Ni^{2+} or Cu^{2+} in solution is evident from the titration curves of 1 : 1 metal-ligand systems which show steep inflection at $a = 4.0$. A gradual colour change from greenish-violet to violet in each titration mixture containing copper ion below pH of inflection also supports formation of the corresponding complex. Highest $a = 4.83$ value in titration curve of copper-TADD system indicates that a hydroxy species $\text{CuA}(\text{OH})^+$ also

exists between pH ~ 9.0 and 11.0 , and its colour is considered to be violet as the intensity of the violet solution persists up to the highest experimental pH. The titration mixtures of the nickel systems are almost colourless under the reported reactant concentrations. The stability constants of the species existing in solution are given in Table 2. Higher equilibrium constant values, ($10^{22.2} - 10^{24.8}$) have been reported earlier in the studies of the complexes of similar larger ring systems 1,4,7,10-

Table 2. Equilibrium constant of the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of TACD and TADD (25 °C, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$)

Reaction ^a	log k^b	
	TACD	TADD
$\text{H}_4\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_3\text{A}^{3+} + \text{H}^+$	-6.82	-8.86
$\text{H}_3\text{A}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{A}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-7.84	-9.75
$\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{HA}^+ + \text{H}^+$	-9.95	-10.80
$\text{HA}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{A} + \text{H}^+$	-10.93	-
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}^{2+}$	19.34	-
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{HA}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-	4.95
$\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}(\text{OH})^+$	-	3.69
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+}$	11.90	-
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{HA}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-	-2.89

^aA = TACD or TADD, ^bvalues are $\pm 0.05\text{--}0.29$

tetraazacyclododecane ([12]-N₄)¹¹, 1,4,7,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane ([14]-N₄)¹² and 1,4,8,12-tetraazacyclopentadecane ([15]-N₄)¹³ with copper and 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane ([14]-N₄, cyclam)¹⁴ with nickel at 25 °C. Comparatively low value of equilibrium constant for nickel and copper complexes of TACD (Table 2) is probably due to smaller ligand cavity size in which the metal ion is not well fitted.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for recording the infrared, ¹H NMR and mass spectra and microanalyses of the compounds.

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